

COLLECTIVE AND PERSONAL TRAUMA IN NJABULO NDEBELE'S THE CRY OF WINNIE MANDELA AND CHIMAMANDA NGOZI ADICHIE'S HALF OF A YELLOW SUN

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Abstract: *This article centers on the portrayal of collective and individual trauma in Njabulo Ndebele's The Cry of Winnie Mandela and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Half of a Yellow Sun. Borrowing concepts from postcolonial theory and trauma studies, the inquiry considers the psychological and historical ramifications of national crises in both novels: apartheid in South Africa and the Nigerian Civil War. This study considers the dual concepts of trauma as expressed by narrative time and the tension between individual experience and collective history. Both texts propose how individuals' suffering is shaped by wider socio-political violence and how storytelling enables the confrontation and catharsis of traumatic pasts. In conclusion, the study attests that these novels serve as literary interventions that contest official history and pave way for the further conceptualization of trauma within post colony African settings.*

Introduction

Trauma, in its simplest psychological explanation, is the intellectual and emotional response to a life-altering or painful experience that overwhelms one's capacity for coping or comprehension. These experiences usually consist of act of extreme cruelty, individual tragedy, systemic oppression forced migration or war. Trauma differs from ordinary stress or adversity; it is a primal rupture which leaves

psychological or emotional Bruises. In literary studies, trauma has emerged as a vital conceptual and analytical instrument practically in the interpretation of works that grapple with the consequences of violence, historical injustice and social disintegration.

Cathy Caruth, arguably the most powerful voice of trauma studies, argues that trauma defies straight forward story telling because trauma is not experienced when it happens, instead trauma

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re-emerges in broken and delayed ways, in the form of involuntary symptoms like flashbacks, nightmares or silences that cannot be so subordinated to control by conscious mind or coherent language.

In her book *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative and History*, Caruth explains that trauma speaks in non-speech, in not speaking and in fragmentation of narrative coherence. This explains why Ndebele Njabulo write the title of the book by mixing letters thus; “tHe CrY oF WiNnIe MaNdeLa” and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s adoption of the non-linear technique by mixing timelines to show fragmentation which reflects the fragmented experiences of traumatized character.

In post-colonial African writing, trauma can be both individualized and collective. It is not merely about psychic harm to the individual but also about community-centered, historical trauma inflicted during colonialism, this we can see in the character for Okonkwo in Achebe’s “*Things Fall Apart*”, civil war, apartheid, example Peter Abraham’s *Mine Boy* genocide and political and political tyranny. Here, trauma writing is a space in which writers resist the silence of colonial and post-colonial states, attempting to recover repressed histories and acknowledge the lasting psychological damage inflicted on subjects and communities.

Writers such as Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie and Njabulo Ndebele treat trauma not only as a method of describing suffering, but as a method of exploring how suffering is remembered,

reported or forgotten. These novels struggle intensely with trauma as individual illness and communal condition shaped by the sorts of historical context that involve the Biafra War and apartheid South Africa. This is why Dominick LaCapra a prominent scholar in trauma studies, contents trauma should not be understood solely in individualistic or clinical terms, rather, it can take on a “structural” character becoming embedded in the socio-political and historical fabric of entire communities and nations. (Writing History, Writing Trauma, 2001).

Collective and Personal Trauma in Njabulo Ndebele’s *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* and Chimamanda

Ngozi Adichie’s *Half of a Yellow Sun*

Trauma, both personal and collective, has emerged as a preoccupying concern in recent African fiction, as a prism through which the violent political and historical legacy of the continent is being worked out. African writers tend to confront the afterlives of colonial occupation, civil war, apartheid, and ethnic conflict, routinely scripting these historical fault lines into intimate narratives of loss, displacement, and survival. In this case, trauma is not only a psychological condition but a complex cultural and narrative genre that is both an expression of individual suffering and collective memory. Njabulo Ndebele’s *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s *Half of a Yellow Sun* are exemplary texts in this regard. Both novels interrogate the psychological and social implications of major

historical events, South Africa's apartheid era in the first and the Nigerian-Biafran War in the second, through the personal histories of their characters. The fictions are grounded in the lived experiences of ordinary individuals, women especially, whose traumas resonate and magnify general national and cultural displacements.

In *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*, trauma is inseparable from the politics of waiting, absence, and fragmented identity under apartheid. Ndebele provides a searing narrative in which four fictional women, the alleged "Waiting Women," reflect on their personal anguish as they wait for husbands who have been politically exiled, imprisoned, or otherwise lost to the anti-apartheid struggle. Their narratives are juxtaposed with that of Winnie Mandela, the political activist and wife of Nelson Mandela, who herself experienced years of separation and isolation. The book reimagines the historical figure of Winnie Mandela as not only a public symbol of resistance but also a private woman who has to balance the price of love, betrayal, expectation, and survival. The convergence of fictional and historical accounts allows Ndebele to explore the ways in which trauma is not only written into political institutions but also reproduced through the emotional and psychic lives of women. The novel offers a unique inquiry into the ways in which gendered trauma is lived out in national liberation struggles, typically edged out by the grand meta-narratives of heroism and political martyrdom.

Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun*, on the other hand, tells the brutal history of the Nigerian Civil War (1967–1970), which led to the unsuccessful secession of Biafra and claimed the lives of millions, primarily through starvation. Adichie situates this horrific history within a web of close personal relationships, anchoring the story to the experiences of characters like Olanna, Kainene, Odenigbo, and Ugwu. They experience various forms of physical and psychological trauma, including rape, dislocation, betrayal, and the long-term effects of post-war amnesia. What is distinct in Adichie's approach is her insistence on humanizing history: rather than giving a didactic account of the war, she evokes the daily, physical, and intimate nature of suffering. In Olanna's observation of the massacre of her family, or Ugwu's reluctant transformation from houseboy to soldier, Adichie uncovers the manner in which trauma inscribes itself onto the personal in frequently unuttered or repressed forms. The novel's non-linearity and use of multiple narratives operate to highlight the decentered and multilayered nature of traumatic memory. Both *Half of a Yellow Sun* and *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* foreground the tension between individual and collective trauma, and the manner in which individual suffering is both dictated by and resistant to master historical narratives. Trauma, in both novels, is not confined to one catastrophic event but is prolonged, cyclical, and intergenerational. This is particularly evident in how silence, absence,

and erasure function in the novels. Ndebele's waiting women are more likely to be dumbfounded by the extremity of their pain, poised between social expectations of stoicism and internal breakdown. Similarly, in Adichie's novel, post-war silence about Biafra in the Nigerian national psyche functions as a metaphor for unworked-through trauma, and characters like Ugwu struggle to write their own counter-narratives in an attempt to undo this erasure. In this manner, memory especially cultural and narrative memory is a fundamental site of resistance, healing, and meaning-making.

Personal Trauma in Ndebele's *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*

In *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*, Njabulo Ndebele uses the waiting metaphor successfully to excavate the psychological landscape of women who were left behind in South Africa's apartheid era. The individual life histories of the four hypothetical "Waiting Women" Deliswa, Mamello, Ruth, and Amandla are widows through which the personal reach of political violence is brought to light. Their story, while romanticized, is rooted in truth, capturing the living reality of many black South African women whose lives were suspended as their husbands were incarcerated, banished, or buried beneath the politics. Waiting is an emotional imprisonment; it is not a static stance but one that is plagued with psychological collapse, loss of identity, and existence anxiety. For these women, personal trauma is inseparable from the political apparatus that controls their lives.

Deliswa, for instance, waits for her husband who goes abroad to study and never returns. Not only is she traumatized by his abandonment, but it also gradually dawns on her that her sense of self and aspirations were intricately linked with his being. Mamello anticipates a husband who has been jailed for political activism, but instead finds public shame when he returns home and accuses her of infidelity. Ruth, a woman of strong religious conviction, anticipates with unwavering belief, only to be wracked with inner conflict and shame. Amandla's story is more defiant, her refusal to wait is a challenge to the idealized notion of fidelity in women. These women's lives unwrap how deeply inner trauma is embedded in gendered myths of womanhood and roles. Ndebele's use of interior monologues, confessions, and flashback narration uncovers the inner burden these women carry, shattered by the impossibility of being supportive wife, moral pillar, and silent sufferer.

Winnie Mandela's inclusion in the text is a revolutionary blending of fictional and historical narrative. By inserting a scripted dialogue between the Waiting Women and Winnie Mandela, Ndebele establishes a space of discourse in which personal grievance is balanced against public myth. As both symbol and subject, Winnie embodies the contradictions of womanhood under apartheid. Both respected for her resistance and defiance of the state and judged for her personal life, particularly her political activism and reputed promiscuity, she encompasses the contradictions of womanhood

under apartheid. In the novel, Winnie is not only a political symbol but also a woman who experiences suffering, betrayal, and moral ambiguity. Her trauma is added to the double expectations of heroism and womanhood, where personal suffering is secondary to political symbolization. As the Waiting Women interrogate Winnie, their exchanges replicate similarities of abandonment, judgment, and survival, developing a fluidity between the political and personal, the ordinary and the extraordinary.

What is presented in these narratives is a complex model of trauma that is gendered and contextual. The trauma of the Waiting Women is not physical brutality but emotional breakdown and psychological displacement through apartheid. The lack of their husbands is not just practical absence but an existential one, and that reveals relational trauma. These women construct themselves in relation, marriage, motherhood, religion, and political allegiance. When these anchors are destabilized or stripped away, they experience identity crises that are difficult to describe. Their harm is silent, unseen, and underrated, echoing a larger culture of discounting women's emotional work and interior lives.

From the part of the novel entitled “Penelope Descendants”, Ndebele gives an overview of what to expect in the novel thus:

So, what does a woman do in the absence of her husband, who is in jail, in the mines, in exile, or is dead, or away studying, or spending most of

the time on the road as a salesman, or who while not having gone anywhere in particular...? This woman has seen all kinds of departures, has endured the uncertainties of waiting, and has hoped for the return of her man. Departure, waiting and return: they define her experience of the past, present and future. They frame her life at the centre of a great South African Story not yet told. (p 1)

Ndebele concludes by saying that “this book tells the stories of four unknown women (which is the aspect of the personal experiences) and that of South Africa’s most famous woman, who waited” (p 1). He goes further by specifying where these women waited who waited come from “one descendant is from the remote mountains of Lesotho. Another is from small township in the East Rand. The third from Soweto. The fourth... Johannesburg... (39).

The first descendant who is from the remote mountains of Lesotho named “Mannete Mofolo” shares her personal traumas of her husband leaving home. According to the author, Lejone Mofolo who is the husband of Mannete Mofolo: ... yields to strong pressure to leave his family of five children. He cannot just sit back and watch the world collapse around him. Drought, the deep highlands of Lesotho have seen no rain for many years... drought has killed all the maize... it is such urges that have driven many men over a century to find themselves in a long queue at a recruiting agency sign up for work in the mines of South Africa? (11)

The first descendant Mannete Mofolo “watch her husband step out of the house early one morning” (11). Her first personal trauma came as time goes by; this is because... “In time, his visits home become infrequent (i.e., Lejone). The money he used to send home trickles to a halt. His language changes.”

Finally, Lejone settles in Benoni, eTswathwa, with a woman from the Northern Transvaal, and starts another family. It is a long proves, but one that, when you look back, seems to have happened suddenly.

Meanwhile “Mannete, back home, waits with increasing anxiety, experiencing her own metamorphosis. At first, she says “it’s never happened that he didn’t return home after nine months”. ‘never’, means in a period of two years. Trusting him, her first thought is that Lejone may have died. Nine months.

Twelve months. Eighteen months. After two years, which still remarkably seems like one month, she panics (14).

Mannete didn’t accept the fact that her husband has abandoned her, this is why the author states, ... and went out in search of her missing husband instead of sitting down and waiting... In a bus, or a taxi, or a train, or walking through the numerous, dizzying city streets... it was as if she had been in a cloud, being carried by a floating feeling: that one and only feeling that lead to some kind of death...this feeling shielded her from remembering the painful burden of knocking on strange doors to ask for a roof to

sleep under... of walking through the night to hospitals, mortuaries, and police stations. (16)

The second descendant’s personal trauma starts when her husband “a man of thirty-five obtains a scholarship to go overseas to study to become a doctor. He leaves behind his beautiful young wife and two children... after three years of effort, he tires”. (17) Deliciwa, a domestic science teacher, sends money to her husband unfailingly every month. (17)

For ten years she waits for her student husband, but her personal trauma was as a result of her infidelity.

Ndebele in the novel narrates Deliciwa’s experiences thus:

In the tenth year of her husband’s medical studies, she discovers she is pregnant. In the twelfth year, her husband finally completes his studies and he returns home in the fourteenth year to find a four years old child.

It all happens fast. In a rage, he accuses her of infidelity and abandons her and “her spoilt children”, now teenagers who “side with her”. Six months after his return, he divorces her and marries a nurse. “Double qualified”. They settled down to a successful medical career (18)

Her personal trauma heightens when she blames herself “for having yielded to a moment’s weakness (20). Her escapades are with Themba, the businessman who ran a butchery and “General Dealers”. (20)

Themba came in at that very moment she had not seen him and his family for some weeks. He dropped in for a ‘surprise’... A fierce

determination then took hold of her. She saw the anguish in Themba's face, but there was no pity in her... he attempted to resist but there was only one pre-determined victory: hers.

The anguish on his face did not last, though... overwhelmed perhaps by years of compassion and the restraints of decency, he finally gave in to what he had always desired. They were swallowed by that moment of moments beyond all knowing. Oblivion (22)

In the novel Ndebele asked a penitent question which is "why did the reality of her situation only come to her once her stomach began to swell with a child who is not her husband's?". (22) He concludes by stating that

"there would be no departure for her now, only the agony of waiting for the return of a man into a moral situation so complex she began to lose confidence in any claim to really know him. (22) The Third Descendant, who decides to recount her ordeals in first person point of view started thus:

I am Mamello Molate, the only child of Phineas and Bridgitte Letlala. I was told by my mother that I came after three miscarriages. Finally, after many years of trying, they got me. I came. Mamello! That's what I meant to them. Patience (23)

She recounts how she fell in love with her husband and her first personal traumatic experience with him thus:

One late afternoon, five years later, I came back home from work as usual. I got down to preparing her evening meal...

By eight o'clock he was still not back. I looked at the wall laid table and grew restive. Where was he to make it complete? Its most unlike my husband, I thought.

I called friends and relatives and we began what people do in township when someone loved does not turn up as expected. We searched through hospitals, mortuaries and police stations: ... To no avail. What I did not know then was that I was not to see my husband for the next ten years. (24) Twelve months later she received a postcard with a "Cuban stamp", that her husband had fled into exile. He had succeeded in keeping his political activities from her. Mamelolo Molete also shares her husband's personal trauma, thus:

He was arrested while on a military incursion and was sentenced to fifteen years on Robben Island. Ten plus fifteen? Twenty-five. I set eyes on him ten years later when he was an awaiting trial prisoner. I visited him in jail dutifully. (25) She further states that when he finally came out of prison, "I received a letter from him in which he announced that he was not coming back to me... it best to bring things to an end" ... (26) She grew numb in shock. After all she had done for him and the waiting. (26) She recounts how she has had five nervous breakdowns (27). After the third breakdown according to her:

Some friends told me about a Sa ngoma who helped women get their husbands back. I laughed it off. Such illness. But alone at home, I began to be obsessed with the idea. I decided to try it.

There I was kneeling naked in the middle of a thatched hut choking with smoke, being smeared all over my body with the fresh warm blood of a goat... Little cuts were made into my body and ointments and goat inyongo rubbed into the cuts... I tasted its bitterness.

Was that me drinking bitter liquids, and then being steamed countless times, kneeling under layers of blankets over a basin of hot water? (27 – 28)

Ndebele explores how Mamello Molete's husband got another wife, a white woman and this led to her fifth nervous breakdown:

A year later, he appeared on Tv in a programme on inter-racial marriages declaring that Annabelle, come what may he had found the meaning of his life. Race had nothing to do with it. He saw in Annabelle a woman, a true companion, not a white woman. (29)

She emphatically states how her husband warned her by asking he to “please, now stay out of my life. There's nothing left between us. It's all over and done with!!! (31) Perhaps she thinks here is the real reason he left, “I am naming my fear only now. Did he fly from my bareness? Surely the child he now has was the fruit of his seed fertilizing a woman's egg. (32)

The Fourth Descendant who is a woman lives with her husband and family. But he openly “sleeps around” ... At first, his absences are barely noticeable, until increasing absence signifies departure... Why should marriage be a punishment, she asks herself?... Our fourth descendant did not know whether what kept her

from having an affair was the fear of such terrible consequences... Was she naïve? It could be quite confusing.

She watched him deteriorate, so saturated with corruption that he began to plan around it... he would proceed to the next rendezvous for the night, perhaps with a woman who was also trying to come to terms with waiting. Certainly, this Penelope's husband had lost both conscience and thought. (37)

She finally lost the man, “she had him buried in a casket, costing thousands of rands which she thought he deserved” (37) This is because she wants to show them that she loved her husband. Her own case of personal trauma was as a result of her husband's infidelity and neglect. According to her, after the burial, she could feel on her shoulders the eyes of the neighbourhood, the eyes of the men and women... Proof of infidelity is the aim of society's interest in the life of a woman who waits for an absent husband (38)

Lastly, *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* locates individual trauma not as a deviation of political discourse but as its affective core. In placing women's voices at the center, the novel counters patriarchal and nationalist discourses that marginalize or instrumentalize women's pain. The novel emphasizes that trauma existed not only on the front lines and in detention but also in bedrooms, kitchens, and empty chairs, spaces where absence created a ghostly presence and where love became an arena of deferred hope. Through this deeply human portrayal of personal

trauma, Ndebele extends the boundaries of political fiction, insisting that the personal is not only political but also profoundly traumatic in its own right.

Collective Trauma and Apartheid's Legacy in *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*

In *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*, Njabulo Ndebele reveals the profound and intricate trauma suffered by black South Africans in shared ways under apartheid. Central to it is the systematic assault on black family life by the apartheid regime, a devastation that was brought about through forced removals, institutional segregation, and the imprisonment or forced labor migration of large numbers of black men. Men's absence, whether in the form of imprisonment, exile, or economic displacement, was not a random by-product but a grand strategy that compelled black women to bear the bulk of emotional, social, and economic survival. In assuming the duties of childcare, moral instruction, and community construction, their emotional and psychological lives became folded into a collective state of deferred hope and suspended identity. The individual trauma of individual women thus stands as synecdoche for a larger communal disintegration, a trauma heard echoing across generations and through memory, silence, and resistance.

Ndebele's fiction puts this communal trauma at the forefront by using the structural device of the "Waiting Women" an aggregate of fictional women whose individual lives are both intimate and communal. Their testimony is not isolated

incidents but a codification of themes in apartheid South Africa's social landscape. Each woman's suffering, be it from betrayal, loneliness, or internalized shame is reflected in others' testimonies, testifying that individual suffering is multiplied and normalized by a culture steeped in systematic injustice. By placing these voices within a collective framework, often intersecting in dialogues and selfreflexive monologues, Ndebele emphasizes that trauma under apartheid was not solitary but embedded in the collective experience of an entire gendered and racialized group. Waiting, therefore, is something beyond the literal and an allegorical condition of suspended liberty, incomplete belonging, and mutual suspension in time.

During this period, Ndebele exposes the ill treatments meted upon the Blacks, thus ...countless arrests, charges, courtroom, drama, interrogation and torture, imprisonments, detentions, restrictions, banning, banishment and the continues absence.

Major Theunis Swanepoel! Do you remember him? The terror of all detainees. Joel Carlson is said to have described him in the following terms: a heavy man, broad across his shoulders, ... His face was pork marked, blotchy pink and purple...

Notorious and feared throughout the land, among the oppressed, he personified the ugly underside of the pomp and ceremony of the opening of apartheid's parliament... The torture chamber (71)

Stated by the novelist they were “so much ugliness... kidnapping children; gruesome beatings and torture of children; disappearance and death; assassinations; defamations and denunciations; intimidations and terror... Major Theunis Swanepoel, who so brutalize you that you have lost all sense of distinction between perception and reality (74)

Ndebele opines that; “campuses; blocked highways; burned to death old women we accused of being witches; abused our children...” (84) “...homes that was raided by policemen whose task was to harass you, your bedroom laid waste before your eyes at each raid” (89). Some if the people of South Africa were ... “sentenced to life imprisonment” (114)

At that time,

They want the people to confess to deeds that they have not done. I refuse. Then the beating resume. And the torture... the questions, the insults, the whispering into your ears that comes with the white man’s revolting hot breath. Somewhere you lose all orientation and everything around you goes whirling round... (119)

Ndebele commitments to portray the South Africa’s experiences during the apartheid era can be seen in his decision to dedicate the novel to Sara Baartman who according to him, “endured the horrors of European eyes, was desecrated beyond her death, and finally returned home to rest”. This alone shows that the novel is all about the collective experiences of the South Africans during the Apartheid era.

These are not passive victims; they are witnesses, keepers of testimony, and heirs of a psychological inheritance forged in the crucibles of apartheid's dehumanizing rationality. In this sense, Ndebele's writing is parallel to Cathy Caruth's contention that trauma is not experienced at the moment of violence but also in the belated, unresolved, and frequently collective response to that violence (Caruth 4). In *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*, traumas in the women are not sealed off by traditional closure but are open sores, markers of stillunresolved history continuing to shape the present.

Notably, Ndebele's interweaving of Winnie Mandela's semi-fictionalized life story with those of the Waiting Women situates her as mediator between the political and personal, the singular and collective. Winnie's life, mythologized and studied, is a site of convergence for black South African women's collective memory. Even as she is necessarily positioned in history as a resistance figure, Ndebele untangles further the psychic cost of her politicized self. Her literal and metaphorical "waiting" on Nelson Mandela, her framing as the "Mother of the Nation," and the controversy that attended her activism encapsulate the contradictions of collective trauma, how an individual becomes the location of shared hopes, pain, and contested memory. Through Winnie, Ndebele makes a point of demonstrating how collective trauma is shared not horizontally across equals but vertically, across generations and within iconic figures who get to bear the psychic toll of history.

Moreover, Ndebele's exploration of collective trauma is also very gendered. The apartheid state's transgressions were not just racial but patriarchal in nature. Women's trauma, structurally attached to the wider social unrest, is deliberately gendered by their own gendered roles. They are expected to be faithful, to suffer in silence, to be full of virtue like their men are hailed as heroes. This gendered expectation increases their collective misery, for the moral responsibility of sustaining the community is placed disproportionately on their shoulders. The fictional women's stories and their meeting with Winnie serve the purpose of overturning such assumptions by asserting that the trauma of the community cannot be accounted for unless the anguish of women who were both symbolically central and structurally peripheral in the struggle against liberation is also considered.

What is also innovative in the narrative of Ndebele is the concept of post-traumatic community. The collective choice of the women to tell their stories albeit retrospectively, prevents a sort of communal healing. It creates a space of testimony in which the memory is witnessed and confirmed, in which silences are broken, and in which the apartheid psychic wounds begin to be called. Communal storytelling is the process that speaks to Dori Laub's assertion that trauma must be witnessed and spoken in order to facilitate any form of integration or healing (Laub 70). In *The Cry of Winnie Mandela*, this witnessing is done by the

literary space of the novel whereby shards of experience solidify into a communal account of suffering, resistance, and incomplete reconciliation.

Lastly, Ndebele's representation of collective trauma in *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* shows that the apartheid state did not only physically and legally dominate but remapped the emotional and relational lives of its subjects. Its lengthening shadows cast not only in the past but also in its continued afterlife in the silences, confessions, and hangover conversations that haunt the women's tales.

Personal Trauma in *Half of a Yellow Sun*

In *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie provides a compelling examination of personal trauma in characters whose lives are torn apart by the brutal realities of the Nigerian Civil War (1967–1970). Perhaps the most graphic description of trauma is that of Olanna, a university teacher from a high-caste Igbo family. Olanna's trauma becomes acutely personal when she travels to Kano and witnesses the killing of her kin in one of the pre-war ethnic pogroms. This traumatic experience not only deranges her psychologically but also dissolves her previously protected worldview. The setting, also famously quoted for its vivid imagery "the pot was on the floor, its contents spilled, and beside it lay a child's head" (Adichie 186), sets her on her path of psychological disintegration. She experiences what in trauma studies is referred to as a dissociative reaction, retracting emotionally and exhibiting physical reactions such as vomiting

and fainting, responses that Judith Herman identifies as characteristic among trauma survivors (Herman 34). Olanna's subsequent numbness and emotional withdrawal illustrate how trauma can make one lose touch with others and with themselves, creating a condition of interior exile even within the familiar terrain of one's own life.

Olanna's trauma is compounded by betrayal when her lover Odenigbo sleeps with another woman, an action that heightens her experience of alienation and fragmentation. While the initial trauma is caused from the outside by the horror of war, this betrayal adds a new level of pain, one which moves beyond the external to mirror the intersection of national conflict and internal collapse. In some way, Adichie uses Olanna's psychological collapse as a metaphor for the fragmentation of the Nigerian state, her inner collapse echoing the national collapse. Moreover, Olanna's silence about the most traumatic elements of her experience underscores what Cathy Caruth describes as the "irrepresentability" of trauma, wherein the most disastrous experiences are impervious to explicit depiction and instead exist in symptom and silence (Caruth 5). This struggle between speaking and silence, between the need to tell and the ability to tell, is central to Olanna's characterization and representative of the psychic cost of surviving mass violence.

Ugwu, the young houseboy brutally reconstituted as a boy soldier, offers another powerful vision of personal trauma. Initially

introduced as hungry, curious, and innocent, Ugwu's experience with war initiates a slow, painful erosion of his moral compass. His induction into the Biafran army, most of all the scene when he is party to the gang rape of a woman, serves as a turning point in the novel's exploration of moral injury and psychological degradation. Ugwu's shame and guilt are genuine; the rape is kept in restraint in the telling, and its terror is embedded in his retrospective silences and guilt. He does not talk openly about the rape for most of the novel, consistent with trauma theory which asserts that the most painful moments are unutterable, remembered only obliquely or in disassociated pieces (Felman and Laub 69). His trauma does not appear in pyrotechnic outbursts or overt despair but in a repressed, chronic sense of inner decay, a moral wound that refuses to heal. Thus, Ugwu is a metaphor for the war to destroy the youth innocence and distort not only the landscape but the inner moral topography of those being drawn into its vortex.

Olanna personal trauma could be seen thus:

She felt bitter towards them at first, because when she tried to talk about the things she left behind in Nsukka – her books, her piano, her clothes, her China, her wigs, her singer, sewing machine, the television – they ignored her and started to talk about something else (190)

Some of their personal traumas is the fact that the characters had to leave their houses. Olanna and her lover Odenigbo left Nsukka to Abba and from Abba to Umuahia when the was became

intense. They live in a house allocated to them by Professor Achara. She laments here:

There was nothing normal about the house. The thatched roofed and cracked, unpainted walls bothered Ugwu, but not as much as the cavernous pit latrine in the outhouse with a rusting zinc sheet drawn across it to keep flies out. It terrified baby. The first time she used it, Ugwu helped her steady while Olanna cajoled her. Baby cried and cried (201)

Most importantly, Olanna witnessed a personal trauma when Odenigbo slept with the maid Amala from Abba. She confronts Odenigbo in this manner:

“You touched Amala,” Olanna said. It was not a question and yet she wanted him to respond as if it were; she wanted him to say no and get upset with her for even thinking that. But Odenigbo said nothing, he sat down on his arm chair and looked at her... she turned towards the kitchen and nearly towards the kitchen and nearly fell beside the dining table because the weight I her chest was too large, not measured to her size (228)

Olanna was so traumatized that she decided to go to Kano, because if there was a place, she could think clearly it was in Kano” (229)

Another important character in the novel is who had her own share of personal trauma is Amala the village naïve girl, when she had Odenigbo’s baby girl. This is due to the fact that she wanted a baby boy not a girlchild. This made the nurse on duty lament that Amala has refused to touch her baby girl thus: “You know her mother has

refused to touch her” the nurse said as she handed the baby to Odenigbo... she has not touched her at all. We are using a wet nurse” (255)

Kainene’s personal trauma can be observed when she felt betrayed by her twin sister Olanna for sleeping with her lover Richard. She was so sad that she “pushed away her plate and sat with her elbow on the table, her chin lightly supported on her collapsed hands. She said nothing for many long minutes (262)

The war also affected the characters greatly. Adichie in a bid to show this thus:

Olanna jumped each time she heard the thunder. She imagined another air raid, bombs rolling out of air planes and exploding in the compound before she and Odenigbo and baby and Ugwu could reach the bunker down the street. Sometimes she imagined the bunker itself collapsing, squashing them all into mud (267)

Odenigbo has his own share of trauma as a result of the war when he lost his mother. Adichie captures it thus:

She went to him. “Ebezina, stop crying”, she murmured. But she did not want him to stop. She wanted him to cry and cry until he dislodged the pain that clogged his throat, until rinse away his sullen grief. She cradled him, wrapped her arms around him... he cried like his daughter "I never did enough for mama" he said finally (339)

In the novel, minor characters like Pastor Ambrose are also traumatized, that have no option than to use prayers to cushion the

traumatic effects. He makes these funny ultrafast as prayers:

God bless his excellency! God give Tanzania and Gabon strength! God destroy Nigeria and Britain and Egypt and Algeria and Russia! In the mighty name of Jesus! Some people shouted amen! From their rooms... and shouted nonsensical words: she baba she baba she baba... (345)

Ugwu's share of trauma was as a result of the war, could be seen when he was conscripted. Adichie vividly described the agonies he felt which is characterized by shaving his "hair with a piece of broken glass", the rough scrapping left his scalp tender, littered with nicks. The mats... crawled with vicious bedbugs" (368)

Olanna felt devastated when Ugwu was taken away by the Biafran soldiers that when she:

Saw the four ragged soldiers carrying a corpse on their shoulders. Wild panic made her woozy. She stopped, certain it was Ugwu's body until the soldier walked silently, past and she realized that the bead man was too tall to be Ugwu... (385)

Olanna was in deep pains that "they had no salt and Odenigbo drank kai-kai every day and Ugwu was conscripted and she had sold her wig" (386)

Olanna's personal trauma apart from the war experiences include the disappearance of her twin sister Kainene.

Miss Adebayo at the end of the war visited to console Olanna, according to her, "grief was the celebration of love, those who could feel real grief were lucky to have loved" (444). Adichie states that:

"It was not grief that Olanna felt, it was greater than grief. She did not know where her sister was. She did not know. She raged herself for not waking up early the day Kainene left for *afia attack* and for not knowing what Kainene wore that morning and for not going with her and for trusting that Inatimi knew where he was leading her... (444)

Olanna was only consoled by her father's assurance that Kainene would be found thus "*Anyi ga-achota ya, we will find her*" (444) which didn't happen.

Olanna's twin sister, Kainene, is another facet of trauma but one characterized by ambiguity, silences, and evaporation. Her character, usually delineated as emotionally circumspect and aggressively independent, is a foil to Olanna's more expressively open temperament. Kainene's disappearance in a humanitarian mission towards the end of the war is accompanied by a form of trauma not rooted in seen violence, but on the ambiguity and unresolved mourning that underlie loss that lacks completion. The psychological state of ambiguous loss, as described by Pauline Boss, is operational here, where the absence of death or verification prevents normal grieving and leaves survivors in suspended emotional stasis (Boss 15). The disappearance of Kainene leaves her lover and relatives with the possibility of never being able to mourn conclusively, again reliving the numerous unfinished fates typical of the post-war period. Disappearance thus doubly serves as

narrative resolution as well as metaphor for the ongoing psychic disruption of the war.

Individual tragedies narrated in *Half of a Yellow Sun* are therefore not random incidents but deeply interwoven into the socio-political existence of the war. Every character's psychological breakdown is an echo of larger historical dislocations: ethnic violence, political upheaval, and the erasure of historical memory. Adichie's characters experience their traumas differently, but they are all bound together by a common experience of being swept up in a moment of national crisis that takes ordinary lives and turns them into psychological battlefields. The book insists that war not just kills, but distorts memory, contaminates intimacy, and reorders the very fabric of identity. Through Olanna's, Ugwu's, and Kainene's story, Adichie commands the reader to recognize the enduring consequences of war, to keep in mind that personal trauma is not a byproduct of history, but its stuff.

Collective Trauma and the Biafran War in *Half of a Yellow Sun*

In *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie gradually constructs the history of the Nigerian-Biafran War as far greater than a historical background as the very shape in which collective trauma is comprehended and experienced. The Biafran War (1967–1970), initiated after the southeastern region of Nigeria, which was predominantly Igbo, seceded to form the Republic of Biafra, left a profound mark on the national consciousness. The devastating

effect of the war large-scale famine, genocide, refugee situation, and political instability is not one of personal experience but communal ones as well. Adichie presents this collective suffering in her compassionate portrayal of war life, where common people become unwilling participants in a national tragedy. The novel's depiction of food queues extending endlessly, bombing of residential areas, and children with kwashiorkor, whose "bellies were swollen, the rest of them pitifully shrunken" (Adichie 276), is a reference to the dehumanizing and mass impact of war. Such imagery goes beyond sensationalism; it presents a real-life, humanized account of mass trauma as an experience.

What sets Adichie's writing on collective trauma apart is her repetitive focus on the collective psyche of the Igbo. Rather than representing trauma as purely psychological, Adichie treats it as cultural, situated in communal rituals, shared silences, and national mourning. The repeated mention of hunger, missing family members, and fading hopes for Biafra are metaphors to the larger existence detachment, loss of life, of country, of identity, and of tomorrow. It is augmented by that sense of betrayal on the part of the majority of the Igbos, who had believed in the goodness of the Biafran cause and were met instead with abandonment and brutish repression. As historian Chima Korie argues, the conflict "left a legacy of victimhood and marginalization that shaped Igbo identity for generations" (Korieh 89). Adichie employs this sense of shared wound to drive her characters'

relationships, memories, and disillusionments, illustrating how trauma is not only internal but also inherited, passed down through cultural memory.

Furthermore, Adichie brings to the fore the mechanisms through which the war trauma has been silenced or occulted in Nigeria's post-war history. The expatriate writer and British protagonist Richard is employed by Adichie as a narrative device for lambasting the willful amnesia that follows most national catastrophes. He broods about how the world and even Nigerians beyond the east forgot Biafra too quickly, and he feels the need to document the fact of what happened in his book *The World Was Silent When We Died*. From the title alone, one gets the sense of loneliness that the Biafrans endured before, during, and after the war a silence literal and metaphoric. As Aleida Assmann suggests in her work on cultural memory, unpublicly acknowledged trauma becomes "unclaimed" and is at risk of being lost or manipulated in collective memory (Assmann 51). Adichie prevents this from happening by rendering *Half of a Yellow Sun* a novel and an archive, an archive which keeps the memory of Biafra alive because the state does not officially acknowledge it.

The Biafran war according to Adichie was characterized by genocide in the sense that the Igbo's were targeted thus:

Many Igbo officers were dead. The killings were organized; she told him about a soldier who said the alarm for a battalion must parade was

sounded in his barracks and after everyone assembled, the Northerners picked out all the Igbo soldiers and took them away and shot them... "they called Colonel Udodi Ekechi" Northern soldiers put him in a cell in the barracked and fed him his own shit. He ate his own shit. Kainene paused, then they beat him senseless, tied him to an iron cross and threw him back to his cell. He died tied to an iron cross. He died on a cross... (141)

The ugly experience of some of the soldiers during this period can be seen in Colonel Madu's character, which he narrates thus:

I didn't know how bad chicken shit smelled until I slept in it for three days. On the third day, Ibrahim sent me some money and kaftan through a small boy and asked me to leave right away. I dressed as a Fulani nomad and walked through the smaller villages (143)

He further states that "Igbo soldiers and Northern soldiers can never live in the same barracks... they cannot impose Gowon on us as Head of State" (143). Adichie in her bid to explore the collective traumas of the characters with regards to their war experience vividly portrayed how "up to five hundred Igbo people have been killed in Maiduguri" (145), according to the ENBC Radio Enugu. These traumatic encounters can also be seen as Obiozo narrates:

"We saw a lorry driver who agreed to carry us, the man said, and Ugwu could tell right away that he was master's kinsman: ... They are killing us like ants... our eyes have seen plenty, *anyi afujugo anya*; Obiozo said; I saw a whole family,

a father and mother and three children, lying on the road to the motor park... a full Catholic church in Sokoto set on fire, pregnant woman split open in Kano... the lucky ones are coming back... (147)

On this same day, as Ugwu visited the train station to offer bread to the returnees, he met a horror sight...

Mats and dirty wrappers were spread all over the platform and people were crumpled down on them, men and women and children crying and eating bread and tending wounds... Ugwu didn't want to go into that ragged bazaar that he steered himself and walked towards a man sitting on the ground with red-stained rag wounds around his head (148)

Adichie in *Half of a Yellow Sun* vividly explores how a whole family was wiped out in Kano during a riot and shortly before the Nigerian Civil War. This she does by telling the story of Uncle Mbaezi and Aunt Ifeka

Olanna's Uncle and Aunt, Arinze's parents.

Uncle Mbaezi lay face down in an ungainly twist, legs splayed. Something creamy-white oozed through the large gash on the back of his head. Aunt Ifeka lay on the veranda. The cuts in her naked body were smaller, dotting her arms and legs lie slightly parted red lips. Olanna felt a watery queasiness in her bowels before the numbness spread over her and stopped at her feet. (150)

Another collective trauma could be seen when Richard's plane touched down Kano. He experienced the gruesome killings of some Igbo

people traveling down to the East. Adichie narrate the story thus:

Nnaemeka turned to go back to his desk. Richard picked up his briefcase. The side entrance burst open and three men ran in holding up long rifles. They were wearing green army uniforms, and Richard wondered why soldiers would make such a spectacle of themselves, dashing in like that, until he saw how red and wildly glassy, they eyes were. The first soldier waved his gun around. "Ina Nyamiri! Where are the Igbo people? Who is Igbo here? Where are the infidels?"

A woman screamed. 'You are Igbo', the second soldier said to Nnaemeka... Nnaemeka knelt down... the rifle went off and Nnaemeka's chest blew open, a splattering red mess, and Richard dropped the note in his hand... The soldiers ran out to the tarmac and into the aeroplane and pulled out Igbo people who had already boarded and lined them up and shot them and left them lying there (155

– 156)

The Biafran War was characterized by several attacks and air raids, which Adichie captures in this manner:

Ugwu heard the sound just before they cut in their cake in the living room, the swift wah-wah-wah roar in the sky... somebody said, 'Enemy plane! Air raid!...' They ran – Master, Olanna holding baby, Ugwu, some guests – to the cassava patch besides the house and lay on their bellies. Ugwu looked up and saw the planes, gliding low beneath the blue sky like two birds of

prey... the first explosion was so loud that Ugwu's ear popped and his body shivered alongside the vibrating ground... The second explosion followed and then the third and fourth and fifth, until he felt the warm wetness of urine in his shorts... (208)

According to Adichie:

“Starvation was a Nigerian weapon of war. Starvation broke Biafra and brought Biafra fame and made Biafra last long as it did. Starvation made the people of the world take notice and sparked protests and demonstrations in London and Moscow and Czechoslovakia. Starvation made Zambia and Tanzania and Ivory Coast and Gabon recognize Biafra, starvation brought Biafra into Nixon's American campaign and made parents all over the world tell their children to eat up... starvation made the International Red Cross call Biafra its greatest emergency since the Second World War (241)

The starvation was so much that according to one of the characters Harrison Richard's houseboy laments thus:

Hunger is bad, Sah. My people are watching the goats' watching the goats?

To see what they are eating, and after seeing they are boiling the same leaves and giving their children to drink. It is stopping kwashiorkor (310)

The above statement depicts the extent people went in order to eat or feed themselves.

The war became devastating to the extent that Kainene and Richard witnessed the death of Ikejide, which Adichie depicts as such:

A piece of shrapnel, the size of a fist, wheezed past. Ikejide was still running and in the moment that Richard glanced away and back, Ikejide's head was gone, the body was running, arched slightly forwards, arms flying around, but there was no head. There was only a bloodied neck. Kainene screamed. The body crashed down near her long American car, the planes receded and disappeared into the distance... (324)

The children at that time were all malnourished as a result of starvation. This could be seen when Mama Oji told Mama Adanna that:

“The child's illness is not malaria. But she keeps giving her neem medicine that does nothing for her... What Adanna has is Harold Wilson syndrome, *wha*”... “Kwashiorkor. The child has kwashiorkor... Adanna's belly was swollen and her skin was sickly tone, much lighter than it was only weeks ago... (346)

As a result of the war, the Biafra people were faced with fuel scarcity. The people could not afford petrol because “it's a pound a gallon” (389)

Adichie incorporate elegy, this we can see when the fake news of Ugwu's death was announced and a service of songs was held on his behalf, the song goes this way:

Naba na ndokwa, Ugwu nab ana ndokwa.

Oga-adili gi mma,

Naba na ndokwa. (340)

At the peak of the civil war,

Three children died in one day. Father Marcel said mass without Holy Communion. A young girl named Urenwa's belly began to grow and

Kainene was not sure if it was kwashiorkor or pregnancy until the girl's mother slapped her and asked, "who? Who did this to you? Where did you see the man that did this to you? The doctor no longer visited because there was no petrol and there were too many dying soldiers to treat. The well dried up. Kainene went often to the directorate at Ahiara to get a water taker, but each time she came back with a vague promise from the director. The thick, ugly odours of unwashed bodies and rotting flesh from the shallow graves behind the buildings grew stronger.

Flies flew over the sores on children's bodies. Bed bugs and kwali-kwata crawled; women would untie their wrappers to reveal an ugly rash of reddened bites around their waists, like hives steeped in blood. Oranges were in season and Kainene asked them to eat oranges from the trees, although it gave them diarrhea, and then to squeeze the peels against their skin because the smell of citrus masked the smell of dirt. (389)

Adichie also portrayed how little children at that time died of kwashiorkor. The child Chidiebele or Chidiebube? Died. According to the novel:

"The child's belly had lately started to look as if he had swallowed a fat ball, how his hair had fallen out in tufts, how his skin had lightened, from the colour of mahogany to a sickly yellow. The other children had teased him often *Afo mmili ukwa* (410)

Trauma is a lens through which the psychological and socio-political effects of colonialism and conflict are revealed. It exposes the deep features

with personal and national narratives and highlights the inadequacies in literature, therefore, serves as both mirror and a mediator of suffering. It reflects the invisible wounds that history has inflicted and provided a space for imagining pathways to healing, reconciliation and transformation. This draws attention to the fact that the word "Trauma" originally in Greek simply means "wound" which in time has developed into a very complex concept.

According to the Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (International Students Edition), trauma is a psychological condition, "a mental condition caused by severe shock especially when the harmful effects last for a long time". It further states that it is an "unpleasant experience that makes you feel upset and anxious (1590). In the book *Abnormal Psychology Current Perspectives 8th Edition* by Alloy, Jacobson and Acocella, at least

Trauma is a severe psychological reaction, lasting at least on month and involving intense fear, helplessness, or horror... such events include assault, rape, natural disaster such as earthquake and flood, accidents, war. This may result to Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). Posttraumatic stress disorder comes from war survivors. (157).

Maria Yellow Horse Brave Heart in her study of Native American communities opines that historical trauma is "the cumulative emotional and psychological wounding over the lifespan and across generations, emanating from massive group trauma experiences (Brave Heart 283).

Trauma is retained not just in books but also enacted through culture, oral traditions and social dysfunctions. Yael Daniel: on his part describes how trauma survivors tend to project, often unwittingly, their unresolved grief and fear onto their children, thus altering the emotional map for subsequent generations (Daniel 10)

Judith Herman, in her classic *Trauma and Recovery* argues that early trauma work focuses disproportionately on war veterans to the neglect of their gender-specific traumas that women have endured, such as domestic violence, sexual assault and reproductive loss (Herman 33).

Trauma theory, as enunciated by Cathy Caruth, provides the grounding from to understand the fractured temporalities and affective geographies within which trauma is enacted in *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* and *Half of a Yellow Sun*. this theory for Caruth is marked by belatedness, this is the fact that the traumatic event is not accessed at the moment but returns in recurrent flashbacks, dreams, and narrative lacunae (Caruth 4). This belated processing infuses trauma with a haunting quality, always disrupting narrative and temporal continuity in conventional ways. According to Kabir Ahmed, trauma is What returns to hunt the victims is not only the violent but also the reality of the way that the violence has not been known fully... it is important to deploy trauma theory to understand the wounds of the history...

Generally speaking, literary artist deploy trauma in various forms just like in Obasikene's work *Chief Okaome* where the playwright exposes the

reader to the traumatic experiences of poor teachers whose salaries are delayed by those in power. this can be seen in the delayed payments; these teachers are faced with the trauma of having to borrow to fend for their families (16 – 18). This draws our minds to Stan and Sali's postulations to them, "Trauma describes the overwhelming, upsetting situations that triggers a person's strong emotions, psychological and physical reaction which can arouse powerful emotions, fear, anxiety, anger and sadness". To Ene Ann Edache and Joy Nwiyi, "Trauma can be life threatening injuries affecting self-esteem and cause mental health impairments... causing overwhelming feeling of misery. Scholarly readings of *Half of a Yellow Sun* and *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* have centered these books in discussions on how African literature engages trauma, memory and silences of history. Several studies analyze them through interdisciplinary lenses including trauma theory, feminist critique and post-colonial discourse. Authors like Chielozona Eze emphasizes hat Adichie's account of the Biafran War presents moral responsibility and ethical obligation to remember (Eze 47). Ato Quayson argues in turn that the fractured narrative structure of the noel mimics the disorienting effect of trauma, opening up space in which "affective responses are mediated" (Quayson 162). These highlights Adichie's commitment to recovering the suppressed histories of Biafra, a war often glossed over or fabricated in Nigeria's official narrative of events.

Similarly, Mag Samuelson contends that the novel's use of mythic intertextuality namely the Penelope trope, reconfigures the apartheid waiting woman as an icon of deferred agency and resilience (Samuelson 71). Methodologically, scholars such as Elleke Boehmer and Kai Easton have noted the employment of literary mode to represent trauma. For Boehmer, African trauma fiction is characterized by narrative experimentation, for instance, fragmentation, temporal dislocation and multiplicity, which all depicts the ruptures of trauma (Boehmer 219). This appears in Adichie's non-linear mode and Ndebele's speculative and polyphonic mode. These narratives strategies accomplish more than reflect trauma; they enact it, drawing the reader into the pain, loss and memory.

Rita Barnard in her study of *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* emphasized the novel's fragmented narrative which blurs the boundaries between fiction and historical reality. She argues, this narrative style mirrors the psychological fragmentation of traumas as well as the disjointedness in a society recovering from the violence and moral ambiguity of apartheid.

Benedicte Ledent analyses Adichie's narrative form as a reflection of historical trauma. Writing in the journal *Callaloo*, Ledent focused on the novel's use of non-linear storytelling, fragmented timelines, and multiple narrators. She asserts that these literary strategies mirror the psychological disorientation caused by war. For Ledent, Adichie's temporal shifts between pre-war, war and post war periods reflect the

characters' internal conflicts, emphasizing how trauma dislocates chronological memory.

While many studies have explored either novel individually, this study will undertake a comparative study examining how collective and personal traumas intersect in the context of apartheid South Africa and Biafran Nigerian Civil War. This comparative angle is crucial because both texts respond to historical ruptures that continue to shape national consciousness in their respective countries. By so doing, providing a deeper study that illuminate shared patterns of loss, resistance and identity formation in African post-traumatic narrative

Conclusion

Since trauma not only reflect in content of the stories but also mirrors how they are told, fragmented, multifaceted and emotionally charged in the two novels, the authors manage to manipulate the narrative voice, time and form to reflect rupture. One of the most impactful techniques by both Ndebele and Adichie is that of multiple voices to dramatize the fractured and collective nature of traumatic experience.

In *The Cry of Winnie Mandela* Ndebele creates a polyphonic novel about four fictional female figures. Similarly, Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun* does employ tripartite perspective in an Olanna-Ugwu-Richard paradigm. Both employ non-linear narrative structures to evoke the traumatic temporality. The last technique that the authors mutually employ is the use of playful intermixing of fiction and nonfiction that is metafiction. the author's also employ their local or indigenous

languages in their novels laced with some literary devices and figures of speech. The novels are powerful instances of how literature is used to interpret trauma. Both novels navigate the blurred lines between personal and communal suffering, showing how internalized injuries and embedded in broader historical and political turmoil, apartheid South Africa and the Biafra war in Nigeria.

Finally, these novels not only symbolize trauma but redefine how trauma is understood in

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African literature. They will not allow trauma to be encapsulated in pathological categories or singularized symptomology. Instead, they insist on its social, historical, and political dimensions. By locating traumas in collective trauma and insisting that one's suffering be aligned with communal histories; Ndebele and Adichie open up new paths for empathy, understanding and healing.

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